

Speculation on Two Level Quantum Carnot Cycle Part II

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In (1) a thermodynamical-statistical mechanical approach is presented for a two energy level quantum system for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. It is shown that classical statistical mechanical efficiency of a Carnot cycle $1 - T_c/T_h$ holds for this quantum system. In this note we argue that the Carnot cycle efficiency holds in general if one uses $\Delta E = \Delta Q - \Delta \text{Work}$ with $\Delta Q/T = \Delta S$ if E and S are state variables as they are. One does not need to perform the two energy level specific integrals presented in (1) because the Carnot efficiency result is guaranteed for any number of energy levels.

Approach of Two Energy Level Quantum System

In (1) a two level quantum system is described by the wavefunction

$$W(x,t) = \sqrt{g} \exp(-iE_1/T) W_1(x) + \sqrt{1-g} \exp(-iE_2/T) W_2(x) \quad ((1))$$

Average energy $\langle W|H|W \rangle = g e_1 + (1-g) e_2$ which may be generalized to:

$$E = \sum \text{over } n \text{ } e_n P(e_n) \text{ for } n \text{ levels} \quad ((2))$$

$$dQ = \sum \text{over } n \text{ } e_n dP(e_n) = T dS \quad ((3)) \text{ and } S = - \sum \text{over } n \text{ } P(e_n) \ln(P(e_n)) \quad ((4))$$

Specific results are obtained for $n=1,2$. In particular:

$dQ = -3b/LL dg$ where b is a constant ((5)) This shows that for $dQ=0 dg=0$ which is the condition of a quantum adiabatic transformation i.e. changing L the box size. For this problem $e_n = b_1 n^2/LL$ where b_1 is a constant. For a system with arbitrary n , with

$$P(e_n) = \exp(-e_n/T) / \sum \text{over } i \text{ } \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((6))$$

Having T proportional to $1/LL$ for a $dQ=0$ path guarantees a quantum adiabatic transformation i.e. $P(e_n/T)$ remains constant. In (2) we argued that a main feature of ((4)) and ((6)) is that:

$$E_{ave} - TS = B(T,L) \quad ((7))$$

In other words there exists a function S which consists entirely of probabilities. If the probabilities depend on e_i , then to make them dimensionless one may introduce parameters e_i/T_i . An interesting result is that there is one overall parameter T (not a set of different T_i), but this requires a T factor for S with S mimicking E_{ave} closely. We have noted in (2) that matters may not be so simple i.e. one may need more than e_i and T , for example S_i the entropy of level i . We have suggested: $P(e_i/T) = \exp(-e_i/T) \exp(S_i/T) / \sum \text{over } n \text{ } \exp(-e_n/T) \exp(S_n/T)$. For a particle in a box with infinite walls $S_i = S_{i,p} + S_{i,x}$ and does not depend on L although $S_{i,p}$

depends on i . S_i, x does not. ((7)) still holds because now $S = \sum_n -P(en) \ln(P(en)) + P(en) \ln(S_n)$, but $B(T) = -kT \ln(C(T))$ where $C(T) = \sum_n \exp(-e_i/T) \exp(S_i/T)$.

This is very similar to the ideal gas form in classical statistical mechanics, where $B(T) = -kT \ln(C(T))$ is Helmholtz free energy where $C(T) = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$. In the classical case, one then uses $e_i = p^2/2m$ and replaces the sum with $\int dp_x dp_y dp_z \int dx dy dz$. In (1) a 1-dimensional box with infinite potential walls is used and one stops at the sum over e_i .

S from ((4)) is of Shannon's entropy form with $P(en) = \exp(-e_i/T) / C(T, L)$ in order to satisfy ((7)) where $B(T, L) = -T \ln(C(T, L))$. The L dependence enters because e_i is proportional to $1/LL$.

If one wishes to apply thermodynamical results to ((7)) one has $E_{ave}(P(en), T)$ where $P(en) = P(n, L, T)$. For $dW_{ext} = 0$ one holds e_i 's constant. Thus L is held constant as well, but T may change. Thus, one changes from variable g or $P(en)$ and L to T and L . Then:

$$dE_{ave}/dT (L \text{ constant}) - S - T dS/dT = dB/dT \quad ((8))$$

As a result, one shifts from the original g, L variables of the two level system to thermodynamic variables L and T .

In particular, the parameter T appears in ((7)) because S is taken to be a function of probabilities which depend on e_i and one wants a dimensionless variable i.e. e_i/T . In other words, if L is held constant, E_{ave} and TS are very much the same function.

As a result, one has general forms which hold for any n i.e. any numbers of levels.

In (1) specific results for the two level system ($n=1$ and $n=2$) are given i.e.

$$E_{ave} = bg/LL + 4b(1-g)/LL \quad ((9a)) \quad dQ = -3b dg/LL \quad ((9b)) \quad dW = 2b/LLL (4-3g) dL \quad ((9c))$$

$$\text{And } g = 1/(1 + \exp(-3b/TLL)) \quad ((9d))$$

As one may see, g and L are the variables used to distinguish between dQ and dW although $g(T, L)$.

In (1) specific integrals for the two level system are calculated for a system A-B-C-D-A with A-B being an isotherm at temperature T_H , CD an isotherm at temperature T_c and BC and DA being both thermodynamically adiabatic and quantum mechanically adiabatic because $dg=0$.

When the integrals are performed it is found that $W = (1 - T_c/T_h) Q_h$.

We argue (and the same argument appears in (3)) that this result is guaranteed not only for the quantum two level system, but for any number of quantum level systems with the formalism given above because E_{ave} and S are state variables. One may calculate work for each piece using:

$-\Delta W = \Delta E_{ave} - \Delta Q$. Given that S is a state function and that there is no entropy change along the adiabats, then $dQ_h/T_h = -dQ_c/T_c$ where $dQ/T = dS$ according to (1). Thus:

-Sum over $\Delta W = -\text{Work total} = \text{Change in } E \text{ from } A \text{ back to } A - (dQ_h + dQ_c)$

, but $\text{Change in } E \text{ from } A \text{ to } A = 0$ so $\text{Work total} = Q_h(1-T_c/T_h)$ ((10))

Thus this result may be anticipated without calculating any integrals for the quantum two or any other level system.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the approach taken to describe a two level quantum system by using g and L as variables where $g=P(e_1)$ and L is the box size changes to an approach using T and L because: $E_{ave} - TS = -kT \ln(C(T,L))$ where $S = \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ and $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / C(T,L)$. L appears because e_i is proportional to $1/L$. A very similar approach which links E_{ave} to TS also applies to an ideal classical gas. $-kT \ln(C)$ is then the Helmholtz free energy. In (1) a two quantum level system goes through a Carnot cycle with two adiabats and two isotherms. Integrals are performed calculating ΔQ and total Work and it is shown that: $\text{Work} = \Delta Q_h (1-T_c/T_h)$, the classical statistical mechanical result for this two level system. We argue that this result follows without performing any integrals for the quantum two level or any level system because E_{ave} and S are state variables. Work for each state is $-\Delta E - \Delta Q$. $\sum \Delta E = \text{the change in } E \text{ from } A \text{ to } A \text{ which is } 0$. Entropy changes only along the isotherms for which $\Delta Q_h/T_h = -\Delta Q_c/T_c$ with $\Delta Q/T = \text{entropy change}$. Thus $\text{Work} = \Delta Q_h (1-T_c/T_h)$. (Note: One may alter $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / \sum_n \exp(-e_n/T)$ by replacing $\exp(-e_i/T)$ with $\exp(-e_j/T) \exp(S_j/T)$ where S_j is the entropy of the pure state j as suggested in previous notes.)

References

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